

Quantification of the total and water-extractable pentosan content in wheat flour using a higher-throughput version of the phloroglucinol colorimetric assay

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1. Introduction

Pentosans are non-starch polysaccharides (NSP) composed of five carbon sugars. In plants, pentosans mainly play a structural function being primarily associated with cell walls. Arabinoxylans (AX) represent the most abundant pentosans in wheat grain constituting around 85% of the total NSP (Kiszonas et al., 2012). The AX chemical structure consists of a backbone of β -D-xylopyranosyl residues (xylose) mono-substituted at the 3 position or di-substituted at the 3 and 2 positions with α -L-arabinofuranosyl residues (arabinose). The arabinose residues may also be substituted at the 5 position with ferulic acid allowing the formation of diferulate or triferulate cross-links. Based on variation in their chemical structure, AX solubility differs, and AX molecules are typically divided into water-extractable (WE-AX) and water-unextractable AX (Ibba et al., 2021). Apart from their structural function in the plant, AX also strongly influence wheat processing and end-use quality mostly affecting flour water absorption and dough viscosity. Besides that, AX constitute the major source of dietary fibers (DF) in wheat grains and their consumption has been associated with several health benefits including immunomodulatory and cholesterol lowering activity, lower incidence of type II diabetes, enhanced absorption of certain minerals, fecal bulking effect, and prebiotics effect (Mendis and Simsek, 2013). Given the DF gap present in the diet of most of the world population, in the last years there has been renewed interest in the quantification of wheat grain AX content with the aim to select wheat lines with higher-AX (and DF) concentration that could contribute to increase the daily DF intake. To reach this objective however, development of a safe, reliable, affordable and rapid method for the AX content analysis is of paramount importance. For this reason, in the present study we report a modification of the Douglas (Douglas, 1981) phloroglucinol colorimetric assay for the analysis of WE-AX and total arabinoxylan (TOT-AX) content in wheat whole meal and refined flour. This method greatly improves the efficiency, throughput and repeatability of the original protocol, being ideal for the screening of a relatively large number of wheat lines within a breeding program.

2. Principle

Pentosan content measurement starts with the solubilization of these molecules in either an acid solution (for the measurement of TOT-AX content) or water (for the measurement of the WE-AX content). The solution with the solubilized pentosans is then mixed with the extraction-colorimetric solution and treated at 99°C. During this step, arabinoxylan and pentosans are hydrolyzed reduced to constituent sugars (xylose and arabinose) which are converted into furfural, an organic compound obtained by the acid catalyzed dehydration of 5-carbon sugars. The furfural molecule then donates electrons to two molecules of phloroglucinol, which condense to form a pink/red precipitate. The concentration of such precipitate is proportional to the content of pentosans in the sample and is measured by analyzing the absorbance of

the sample at both 552 and 510 nm and by later subtracting the A_{510} absorbance values to the A_{552} absorbance values in order to remove the influence of the hexose sugars (Kiszonas et al., 2012). The furfural/phloroglucinol complex derived from pentoses in fact exhibits a maximum absorbance at 552 nm and a poor absorbance at 510 nm. Differently, the furfural/phloroglucinol complex formed from hexoses had the same absorbance at 552 and 510 nm indicating that by calculating the difference in absorbance between 552 and 510 nm it is possible to obtain a more specific quantification of the pentoses (Rouau and Surget, 1994). Using a calibration curve obtained with different xylose (pentose) standards of known concentration, the pentosan content present in the analyzed samples is then quantified and given as mg of xylose per gram of sample.

3. Analysis throughput

Given that the flour samples have been already weighted into their relative 2 mL tubes, this protocol allows the analysis of around 150 samples per day by two trained technicians. The analysis refers to the quantification of either TOT-AX or WE-AX content.

4. Materials

4.1 Suggested equipment

Table 1. List of suggested equipment necessary for the analysis of the pentosan content

Equipment	Characteristics	Model and brand
Microplate spectrophotometer	510 and 552 nm	Epoch, BioTek
ThermoMixer	With Thermoblock for 2 mL tubes	C, Eppendorf
Microcentrifuge	For 2.0 mL tubes	Model 5417R, Eppendorf
Analytical balance	Maximum capacity 220 g Resolution 0.0001 g	Explorer, OHAUS
Vortex	-	Genie, SI
ELISA 96-well microplates	400 μ l, 96 well flat	MaxiSorp, Thermo Scientific NUNC
Micropipette	20-200 μ L, 30-300 μ L, 10-100 μ L, 100-1,000 μ L	Eppendorf
Micropipette tips	1-300 μ L clear, wide bore 200 μ L tips yellow 1000 μ L graduated tips blue	Axygen TipOne TipOne
Stop clock	-	-
Microcentrifuge tubes	Safe-Lock Tubes 2.0 mL Graduated tubes 2 mL	Model 0030 120.094, Eppendorf Model 3765.X Neptune
Magnetic stirrer	SP88857104- Aluminum top, stirring Hotplate Speed range 0 – 1500 rpm	Thermo Scientific, Cimarec +
Magnetic bars	Stir bar disp 1/2 X 1/8	Fisher brand

4.2 Reagents

Table 2. List of reagents necessary for the analysis of the pentosan content

Reagents		Chemicals	Preparation	Suggestions
1	Xylose Standard 0.2 mg/mL	Xylose: Fluka cat. No. 95730-25G	Dissolve 20 mg D-(+)-xylose in 100 mL distilled water (in a volumetric flask).	Stable at -20°C for several months. Store in aliquots.
2	Sulfuric acid 1M	Sulfuric acid: JT Baker, 95%	Add 56 mL of sulfuric acid to 944 mL of distilled water.	Stable at room temperature.
3	Sulfuric acid 0.1M	Sulfuric acid: JT Baker, 95%	Add 5.6 mL of sulfuric acid to 994.4 mL of distilled water.	Stable at room temperature.
4	Acid bulk solution	Acetic acid: JT Baker; Hydrochloric acid: JT Baker	Mix 55 parts of acetic acid with one part of hydrochloric acid (55:1). For example, mix 110 mL of acetic acid with 2 mL of HCl.	Stable for 15 days at 4°C. Remove from the fridge at least 2 hours before its use.
5	Glucose 1.75% (w/v)	Glucose: Sigma G5767	Dissolve 1.75 g of glucose in 100 mL of water.	Stable at -20°C for several months. Store in aliquots.
6A	Phloroglucinol 20% (w/v) for TOT-AX from whole meal	Phloroglucinol: Sigma Aldrich; Ethanol: JT Baker	Dissolve 20 g of phloroglucinol in 100 mL absolute ethanol.	Stable for 15 days at 4°C. Light sensitive.
7A	Phloroglucinol and Glucose bulk solution (TOT-AX from whole meal)	-	Mix 5.4 parts of reagent 6A with one part of reagent 5 (5.4:1). For example, mix 5.4 mL of reagent 6A (phloroglucinol 20% w/v) with 1 mL of glucose 1.75% (reagent 5).	Stable for 15 days at 4°C. Light sensitive.
8A	Extraction solution for TOT-AX from whole meal (93% glacial acetic acid (v/v); 1.7% (v/v) hydrochloric acid; 0.86% (w/v) phloroglucinol; 0.014% (w/v) glucose)	-	Mix 18.6 parts of reagent 4 with 1 part of reagent 7A (18.6:1). Example: mix 186 mL of the acid bulk solution (reagent 4) with 10 mL of the phloroglucinol and glucose bulk solution (reagent 7A).	Prepare fresh the day of the extraction. Light sensitive.
6B	Phloroglucinol 10% (w/v) for refined flour and WE-AX from whole meal	Phloroglucinol: Sigma Aldrich; Ethanol: JT Baker	Dissolve 10 g of phloroglucinol in 100 mL absolute ethanol.	Stable for 15 days at 4°C. Light sensitive.
7B	Phloroglucinol and Glucose bulk solution (refined flour and WE-AX from whole meal)	-	Mix 5.4 parts of reagent 6B with one part of reagent 5 (5.4:1). For example, mix 5.4 mL of reagent 6B (phloroglucinol 10% w/v)	Stable for 15 days at 4°C. Light sensitive.

			with 1 mL of glucose 1.75% (reagent 5) .	
8B	Extraction solution for refined flour and WE-AX from whole meal (93% glacial acetic acid (v/v); 1.7% (v/v) hydrochloric acid; 0.43% (w/v) phloroglucinol; 0.014% (w/v) glucose)	-	Mix 18.6 parts of reagent 4 with 1 part of reagent 7B (18.6:1). Example: mix 186 mL of the acid bulk solution (reagent 4) with 10 mL of the phloroglucinol and glucose bulk solution (reagent 7B).	Prepare fresh the day of the extraction. Light sensitive.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the protocol used to determine (A) the TOT-AX content in whole meal; (B) the TOT-AX content in refined flour; and (3) the WE-AX content in whole meal and refined flour.

5. Methods

5.1. Analysis of the total pentosan content in whole meal

A summary of the protocol is reported in Figure 1A. Using this protocol, an average coefficient of variation of 10% is obtained. In order to obtain more robust and reliable results, it is recommended to run all the samples in duplicate, ideally during different days.

Pentosan acid solubilization

1. Weigh 10 mg (+/- 0.5 mg) of whole meal in a 2 mL tube (Safe-lock Eppendorf)

Note: Try to always include in the analysis two samples of known pentosan concentration (high and low) as controls.

Note: The particle size of the whole meal sample could influence the results and typically, the finer the sample, the better the extraction and the higher the values obtained.

2. Add 1 mL of **reagent 2** (Sulfuric acid 1M) to each tube. Vortex for 5 seconds.
3. Incubate the sample in a ThermoMixer equipped with a Thermoblock specific for 2 mL tubes for 10 minutes, at 99 °C and 1,000 rpm.
4. Transfer the tubes in ice for 3-5 minutes and centrifuge for 5 minutes at 5,000 g.
5. Transfer 300 µL of the supernatant in a new 2 mL tube together with 1500 µL of distilled water to obtain a final volume of 1800 µL.
6. Mix by vortex for 5 seconds.

Pentosan extraction and color reaction

7. Dilute 75 µL of the diluted supernatant with 75 µL of distilled water in a new 2 mL tube (safe-lock, Eppendorf).

Note: It is suggested to prepare now the phloroglucinol-extraction solution (reagent 8A) by mixing the reagent 4 and reagent 7A.

8. Add to each tube 750 µL of the phloroglucinol-extraction solution (**reagent 8A**). Vortex for 5 seconds.

Note: From this point also include the samples for the development of the standard curve (steps 1 and 2 of paragraph 5.4) and treat them as reported in the following steps (9-11).

9. Incubate the samples in a ThermoMixer equipped with a Thermoblock specific for 2 mL tubes for 23 minutes, at 99 °C and 700 rpm.
10. Immediately place the tubes in ice for 3 to 5 minutes.
11. Transfer 300 µl by duplicate to a microtiter plate (ELISA plate) and read immediately in a spectrophotometer at 552 and 510 nm. It is necessary to include a water blank and a standard xylose curve in the plate.

Note: Read the absorbances in the spectrophotometer as soon as possible as the color fades.

12. For the calculation of the sample pentosan content follow the steps reported in **paragraphs 5.4 and 5.5.**

5.2. Analysis of the total pentosan content in refined flour

A summary of the protocol is reported in Figure 1B. Using this protocol, an average coefficient of variation of 15% is obtained. In order to obtain more robust and reliable results, it is recommended to run all the samples in duplicate, ideally during different days.

Pentosan acid solubilization

1. Weigh 10 mg (+/- 0.5 mg) of refined flour in a 2 mL tube (Safe-lock Eppendorf)

Note: Try to always include in the analysis two samples of known pentosan concentration (high and low) as controls.

2. Add 1 mL of **reagent 3** (Sulfuric acid 0.1M) to each tube. Vortex for 5 seconds.
3. Incubate the sample in a ThermoMixer equipped with a Thermoblock specific for 2 mL tubes for 10 minutes, at 99 °C and 1,000 rpm.
4. Transfer the tubes in ice for 3-5 minutes and centrifuge for 5 minutes at 5,000 g.

Pentosan extraction and color reaction

5. Follow the steps 7 to 11 as reported for the TOT-AX extraction in whole meal (**paragraph 5.1**) and use as extraction solution the **reagent 8B**. For the calculation of the sample pentosan content follow the steps reported in **paragraphs 5.4 and 5.5**.

5.3. Analysis of the water-extractable pentosan content in whole meal and refined flour

A summary of the protocol is reported in Figure 1C. Using this protocol, an average coefficient of variation of 15% is obtained. In order to obtain more robust and reliable results, it is recommended to run all the samples in duplicate, ideally during different days.

Pentosan water solubilization

1. Weigh 10 mg (+/- 0.5 mg) of whole meal or refined flour in a 2 mL tube (Safe-lock Eppendorf)

Note: Try to always include in the analysis two samples of known pentosan concentration (high and low) as controls.

Note: The particle size of the whole meal sample could influence the results and typically, the finer the sample, the better the extraction and the higher the values obtained.

2. Add 1 mL of distilled water to each tube and vortex for 5 seconds.
3. Place the tubes on a magnetic stirrer with a mini magnet inside each tube and keep stirring for 30 min. At the end centrifuge the tubes for 10 min at 2,500 g.

Pentosan extraction and color reaction

4. Follow the steps 7 to 11 as reported for the TOT-AX extraction in whole meal (**paragraph 5.1**) using the **reagent 8B** as extraction solution. For the calculation of the sample pentosan content follow the steps reported in **paragraphs 5.4 and 5.5**.

5.4. Standard curve preparation

1. Prepare the standard xylose solutions as described in table 3

Table 3. Xylose standards volumes for the calibration curve

Xylose, mg	Xylose stock (0.2 mg/mL), μ l	Distilled water, μ l
0	-	150
0.002	10	140
0.005	25	125
0.010	50	100
0.015	75	75

2. Mix 150 μ L of each standard with 750 μ L of the phloroglucinol-extraction solution (**reagent 8A** for TOT-AX from whole meal and **reagent 8B** for TOT-AX from refined flour and WE-AX from whole meal and refined flour) by duplicate and treat each sample as described from point 9 to 11 of **paragraph 5.1**.
3. Measure in duplicate the absorbance of the xylose standards at 552 and 510 nm for each replicate.
4. Subtract the absorbance of the first standard (0 mg of xylose) from the absorbance of the other standards (0.002, 0.005, 0.010 and 0.015 mg xylose) and then calculate the difference in the absorbance at 552 and 510 nm ($\Delta A_{std} = A_{552} - A_{510}$) by using the average absorbance values obtained from the two replicates.
5. Use the obtained ΔA_{std} difference values and plot them against the xylose mg of each standard to obtain the linear equation associated with the calibration curve (equation (1)).

$$(1) \Delta A_{std} = a * \text{Standard xylose (mg)} + b$$

5.5. Calculation of the sample pentosan content

1. Determine in duplicate the absorbance of each sample at both A_{552} and A_{510} , subtract from each value the absorbance value of the blank and then subtract the average absorbance of the A_{552} to the average absorbance at A_{510} to obtain ΔA ($\Delta A_{sample} = A_{552} - A_{510}$).
2. Estimate the mg/g of pentose present in the sample by using the equation (2) for the determination of the TOT-AX in whole meal or the equation (3) for the determination of the TOT-AX and WE-AX content in refined flour and the WE-AX content in whole meal.

$$(2) P = \frac{[(\Delta A_{sample} - b) * V1 * V2]}{a * F * A1 * A2} * 1000$$

$$(3) P = \frac{[(\Delta A_{sample} - b) * V1]}{a * F * A1} * 1000$$

Where:

P = Pentosan content of the analyzed sample expressed in mg/g

ΔA_{sample} = Difference of absorbance between 552 nm and 510 nm for each sample ($A_{552} - A_{510}$)

a = Slope of the xylose calibration curve. The value varies based on the curve.

b = Intercept of the xylose calibration curve. The value varies based on the curve.

F = Mass (mg, as is) of the flour used for the analysis (10 mg)

V1 = Volume (μL) used to solubilize the pentosans (step 2 of the protocol, 1,000 μL)

A1 = Volume (μL) of the aliquot used to extract the sample (step 7 of the protocol, 75 μL)

V2 = Volume (μL) used to dilute the sample after the acid solubilization step (step 5 of the protocol, 1800 μL)

A2 = Volume (μL) of the aliquot used to dilute the sample after the acid solubilization step (step 5 of the protocol, 300 μL)

1000 = Factor used to convert the results from mg/mg into mg/g

Note: The calculation of the pentosan content can be simplified by using the excel file “AX Calculation Sheet”

6. Troubleshooting

Table 4. List of possible problems that could be encountered while performing the protocol, and possible solutions.

Problem	Possible Cause	Solution
Acid bulk solution freezing	Temperature shock	Remove the acid bulk solution from the fridge at least 2 hours before its use.
Low result repeatability	Sample particle size	Mill the sample to finer and more homogeneous particles
Poor color development of the samples	Reagent quality	Preferably use new reagents or those that have been stored for a shorter time
	Extraction temperatures	Make sure the ThermoMixer reaches 99°C during the extraction step
	Flour particle size (especially for whole meal TOT-AX)	Mill the sample to finer and more homogeneous particles
Poor color development of the standard curve	Shelf life of xylose solution	We observed that the stability of the xylose solution is approximately one month, however, if the tone intensity decreases, reduce the storage time of this solution

7. References

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